

Innovative and Sustainable Groundwater Management in the Mediterranean

D2.3 Report on Regional Groundwater Trends and Their Controlling Factors

VERSION 1.0

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Executive Summary

The overall objective of the InTheMED project is to implement innovative and sustainable management tools and remediation strategies for MED aquifers (inland and coastal) in order to mitigate anthropogenic and climate-change threats by creating new long-lasting spaces of social learning among different interdependent stakeholders, NGOs, and scientific researchers in five field case studies. These are located at the two shores of the MED basin, namely in Spain, Greece, Portugal, Tunisia, and Turkey.

InTheMED will develop an inclusive process that will establish an ensemble of innovative assessment and management tools and methodologies including a high-resolution monitoring approach, smart modelling, a socio-economic assessment, web-based decision support systems (DSS) and new configurations for governance to validate efficient and sustainable integrated groundwater management in the MED considering both the quantitative and qualitative aspects.

This is the Deliverable 2.3, which summarises the work of Task 2.3: "Regional Groundwater Trends and Trajectories Analysis and Their Controlling Factors". This report analyses the quantitative status of groundwater bodies in the Mediterranean region to identify variations and significant changes. The study utilises historical groundwater level data to identify trends and significant changes, with a focus on detecting trends in groundwater levels. The study uses a statistical method called Mann-Kendall (MK) to identify trends and applies three different versions of the MK test. The study found that 40% of wells showed significant trends, with 63% of those showing declining and 37% showing rising levels. Most piezometers did not have a significant trend, ranging from 60% of the piezometers in the different countries. Nine clusters of piezometers were grouped based on their trend results in each decade in the 1985-2014 period, and then classified based on their evolution in stable, declining and rising. Stable clusters were related to highly productive aquifers, temperate climate with year-round precipitation, higher average precipitation and further away from irrigation areas than the others. Declining wells were more related to arid climates, moderately productive aquifers and proximity to irrigation areas. Rising wells were related mostly to higher rates of precipitation increase across the three decades and distant from cities.

1. Introduction

The Mediterranean region is facing significant water security challenges due to the increasing water demand and the effects of climate change. In this context, groundwater has become a crucial resource for irrigation and water supply in the region since the mid-20th century. Groundwater is a strategic resource for domestic supply, agriculture, and other economic activities but is also an essential part of ecosystems. Intense groundwater abstractions exceeding recharge can lead to long-term depletion with catastrophic consequences on streamflow and groundwater-dependent ecosystems, as well as land subsidence and salt-water intrusion in aquifers. However, the budget of this resource remains poorly understood, which makes it challenging to manage sustainably. Analysing historical groundwater level data is one way to identify variations in the quantitative status of groundwater bodies across the region and to understand their complex dynamics. Groundwater level changes are influenced by several factors such as climate variability, recharge patterns, soil permeability, hydrogeology, land use, and groundwater abstraction.

One of the objectives of InTheMED is to strengthen the understanding of groundwater functioning and trends. Work Package 2 is focused on acquiring historical MED data, analysing and sharing of collected data, and enriching data availability, using the High-Resolution Monitoring Approach (HRMA) in case studies characterised by limited data conditions. This report aims to characterise the changes in groundwater storage with a regional perspective, using the available groundwater quantity data from monitoring networks. As this Work Package was done with a regional perspective, the analysis of France is also included despite not being one of the partner countries of this project. First, an overview of the available time series data is conducted. Then, a description of the methods and results is analysed.

2. Data and Methods

In Deliverable 2.2 (Chavez Garica Silva, R., & Jomaa, S., 2022), the collection of groundwater level time series is described in detail. A large portion of them is not centralised and openly accessible, resulting in a lack of detailed assessment of groundwater status at the regional Mediterranean scale. The groundwater monitoring networks of the partner InTheMED countries were analysed to understand the existing data. Furthermore, data that was openly accessible was collected, developing a database with over 9,500 piezometers.

2.1. Collected Time Series

All MED partner countries have groundwater-level monitoring systems. National scale authorities enforce monitoring requirements, while subnational authorities, either province or river basin operators, handle monitoring and data production for the local groundwater bodies. In some cases, like Greece, Portugal, Spain, and Turkey, the data is collated and centralised by the national authority to build a national database. In other cases, the data are sparse in the different subnational authorities with different formats, captured variables, and quality standards, like in Italy and Tunisia.

We have built a database by obtaining data from several sources, processing it for quality checks and metadata creation, and then structuring the data into a standard format. We tailored a strategy for each country with the rationale of obtaining the most extended possible time series from official sources. These strategies have included so far:

- Downloading data from centralised national monitoring systems. This was the case for Portugal and Spain.
- Requesting the data from sub-national authorities without a centralised national system. This was the case for Italy.
- Requesting local researchers to help obtain data where language barriers or data-sharing policies made it difficult to consult directly with the relevant authorities. This was the case for Greece and Tunisia.
- We have also collected data from public reports and published research. In Turkey, groundwater level data sharing is very restricted.

Table 1. Existing groundwater data in different MED countries and their availabilities

Country	Institutional data storage	Approximate amount of stations in the network	Approximate frequency of measurement	Publicly available online and gathered data	General length
Greece	Centralised	1,392	Seasonal, some annual	Yes	From 2010 to 2021 with gaps
Italy	Regional	3,970	Varies within regions from every three days to monthly	No	Increase of measurements in 1980 and 2000
Portugal	Centralised	990	Monthly (some daily)	Yes	Increase of measurements since 1980
Spain	Centralised	2,890	Monthly	Yes	Increase of measurements since 1985
France	Centralised	5,519	Weekly	Yes	Increase of measurements since 1960
Tunisia	Regional	3,100	Twice a year	No	Highly variable
Turkey	Regional	2,748	Varies from weekly to monthly	No	From 1970 on

We have obtained groundwater level data from 9,500 piezometers across the region, including all the countries in study cases of the InTheMED project and France. The time series lengths, frequency and completeness are contrasting (Table 1). More data has been collected from countries with a central monitoring network that provides a data-sharing platform (Portugal, France and Spain). From the collected and processed data, groundwater level measurements started concentrating after 1980. Cumulatively, only 13% of the time series have 30 years or more of measurements, making it challenging to do long-term analysis. In Turkey, we collected data from only 27 stations; the figure does not reflect the growth of the network. In Greece, the data collected is for seven years only. In the case of Tunisia, the data processing of time series the processing of the data has not been completed as the sources. For these reasons, trends have only been calculated for Spain, Portugal, Italy and France.

2.2. Methodology

In this phase of our work, we focused on detecting trends in groundwater levels. Over time, changes can occur slowly or abruptly, and there are various statistical methods that can determine if such changes are significant. The choice of method depends on several factors, such as the length of the time series to ensure a sufficiently large sample, the correlation of one data point to the last one (autocorrelation), and the frequency of the measurements. The Mann-Kendall (MK) test is a widely used method for detecting trends in hydrological and groundwater levels. This test is based on ranking and does not require the assumption of normal distribution, which is often required by other methods. Studies by Fang et al. (2019), Lasagna et al. (2020), Lopez et al. (2015), Mirabbasi et al. (2020) and Ribeiro et al. (2015) have also used the Mann-Kendall test for similar purposes. Therefore, to detect trends in groundwater levels, we used the MK statistical method. We applied three different versions of the MK test to the annual average of water table depths using a programming tool called pyMannKendall. The original MK test does not account for a phenomenon called autocorrelation, which can result in noise or false detections in the presence of trends. To address this, we tested a modification that removes autocorrelation before applying the test, as well as another modification that adjusts the variance based on the autocorrelation. The three tests identified trends in 40%, 14%, and 35% of the wells, respectively. To better understand the data, we also tested for autocorrelation using a test called Durbin Watson,

which showed a strong positive autocorrelation for most wells. Previous analysis revealed that the autocorrelation can lead to underestimating the presence of trends when using the pre-whitening modification (Yue and Wang, 2004). Therefore, we used the Hamed-Rao modification as the primary method for detecting trends.

At first, groundwater level trends were assessed for the entire period of all piezometers with at least ten years of data from Spain, Portugal, Italy, Turkey and France. A total of 7,179 piezometers were assessed at first. Then, at the moment of this report, only for Spain, Portugal and France, for the period between 1985 and 2014, trends were calculated for each decade to understand the dynamic of significant changes beyond one single trend direction and magnitude per time series.

Then the wells were clustered based on their trend results. The trend result and magnitude (Sen slope) for each decade between 1985 and 2014 were calculated, providing a comprehensive analysis of groundwater level changes over time. Next, we employed K-Means Clustering, a popular clustering algorithm, to group the 844 observation wells based on their trend direction and Sen slope for each decade. K-Means Clustering partitions the wells into distinct clusters by minimising the within-cluster sum of squares, ensuring that wells with similar groundwater level behaviours are grouped.

Precipitation data was obtained from the gridded database E-OBS (Cornes et al., 2018), while potential evapotranspiration was obtained from Global Land Evaporation Amsterdam Model (GLEAM v3.7a) database (Martens et al., 2017; Miralles et al., 2011). Grid cells that either overlapped with or were in close proximity to the observation wells under examination were used to isolate time series of daily actual and potential evapotranspiration data.

The proximity of wells to urban areas and potential irrigation zones was assessed using the CORINE land cover dataset of 2018, with a resolution of 100 m. Urban areas were defined as contiguous pixels covering at least 1,500 ha and classified as continuous urban fabric, discontinuous urban fabric, and industrial or commercial units in the CORINE database. Potential irrigation areas were identified as contiguous pixels covering at least 1,000 ha and classified as permanently irrigated rice fields, vineyards, fruit trees and berries, plantations, and annual crops associated with permanent crops, as well as complex cultivation patterns. To

determine proximity, the Euclidean distance from each well to the nearest relevant land use area was calculated using the NNJoin plugin in QGIS.

3. Results

3.1. Entire Time Series

Out of the piezometers with a significant trend (40% with Hamed-Rao test), 63% had an increase of WTD (increasing depth related to depletion) and 37% a decrease. In the three analysed countries, the majority of the piezometers did not have a significant trend, ranging from 60-66% of the piezometers (Table 2). France had the highest percentage of increasing trend results, closely followed by Spain. Spain had the highest percentage of piezometers with a decreasing WTD. In the three countries, piezometers with an increasing trend exceed those with a decreasing trend. While there is a similar distribution, it is important to notice that these tests reveal the trend along the entire time series, and any comparison should be careful, as the piezometers in the three countries have different starting times of measurement. As an example, some piezometers with overall increasing depth were observed in the near proximity to piezometers with overall decreasing depth. When looking closer, the overall increasing depth belonged to piezometers with several decades of data that had undergone depletion and a steady increase of depth but later had a ‘recovery phase’ in the last decade. In contrast, the ones with overall decreasing depth had only been installed the last decades and only picked up on the ‘recovery phase’ of decreasing depth.

Table 2. MK trend test results for the entire period of each well with more than 10 years of data

Country	Number of wells	Percentage of wells		
		No significant trend	Increasing depth	Decreasing depth
France	3,548	66%	24%	11%
Spain	1,557	60%	22%	18%
Italy	1,517	69%	13%	18%
Portugal	533	66%	16%	17%
Turkey	24	25%	71%	4%

Sen Slope is used to determine the magnitude of the apparent trends. This method calculates the median of all slopes between data pairs. The slope reflects the change of WTD, measured in meters, in an annual scale so that it can be understood as the change of meters per year in a piezometer. For piezometers with a significant trend to increase depth, most of the rates of change (57%) are increasing in the range 0-0.2 meters per year, and up to 17% have a change rate from 0.2-0.4 meters per year; and up to 7% of the piezometers have a change rate greater than 1 meter per year. In the case of the piezometers with decreasing depth, also the majority (59%) is concentrated between 0-0.2 meters of decreasing depth per year, while up to 11% have a decrease of depth of more than 1 meter per year. The largest change rate of groundwater level has concentrated in the southwest area of France, and the southeast area of Spain (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Sen slope distribution of overall groundwater level change

3.2. Decades Analysis

After analysing the entire time series on each piezometer, an analysis was made for three decades in order to compare the changes from one period to another. This way, piezometers that had enough data were chosen for trend analysis from 1985 until 2014 in three segments (1985-1994, 1995-2004, 2005-2014), resulting in the analysis of only 843 piezometers. It was possible to compare the amount of piezometers with a certain trend in the different periods

to understand general trajectories of stability, increasing and decreasing WTD. The amount of piezometers with no significant trend fluctuated across the time periods (Figure 2), having the most (80%) in the second period. This is relevant as in the first period the amount of piezometers with an increasing WTD trend (associated to depletion) was up to 23%, and then decreased to 13% in the second and third period. While the amount of piezometers with a decreasing WTD increased from 7% in the first and second period to 19% in the third period. These trajectories indicate a potential process of recovery from some depleting groundwater bodies.

Figure 2. Decade trend change from 1985-2014

When looking at the spatial distribution of the decade analysis (Figure 3), a recovery process can be seen in the north of France, going from increasing depth piezometers populating the center of the country and the southwest in 1985-1994, to then no trend and decreasing trends in 1995-2004 and then a bigger abundance of decreasing trend in the last decade. In a more dispersed manner, a similar process can be seen in Spain. However, in Portugal, the opposite can be seen. While the first two decades show a mix of results, the last decade shows a more prevalent concentration of increasing WTD across the country.

Figure 3. Spatial distribution of decade analysis

All wells were grouped by their groundwater level evolution in the described decades. Grouping wells with similar groundwater level evolutions is useful for analysing and understanding the groundwater status in Spain, Portugal, and France. On one side, it allows us to identify distinct patterns and trends within the data, providing insights into groundwater levels' spatial and temporal variability. This approach allows us to identify commonalities and differences among the observation wells, providing a clearer understanding of regional groundwater dynamics and aiding in formulating targeted management strategies. In our study, we formed nine clusters comprising observation wells (OWs) with similar trend patterns in groundwater level. The mean of the normalised WTD for each cluster is depicted in Figure 4. These clusters are well distributed across the study area, as shown in Figure 5, with notable concentrations in certain regions. Within individual aquifers, OWs either belong to the same cluster or others that exhibit similarities. We classified the clusters based on the evolution of their WTD into three categories: stable, declining, and rising levels (Figure 4).

Figure 4. By grouping the Nine WTD development archetypes could be clustered to describe the changes in the region, with general behaviours of groundwater storage stability (left), decline (centre) and rising (right).

The clusters with stable WTD evolution (Clusters 0, 3, and 1) exhibit no significant trends for most of the analysed periods and display smaller changes in WTD compared to the other categories. For example, despite dry summers and groundwater use for irrigation in the Algarve region (Figure 5), most OWs belong to Cluster 0, showing no discernible trends over the three decades. Additionally, a few OWs belong to Cluster 1, which demonstrates a gradual rise in WTD during the last decade.

Figure 5. Spatial distribution of wells distributed by cluster types with a background by climate type

The clusters with declining WTD evolution (Clusters 4, 6, and 2) exhibit notable declines in at least one of the analysed periods. Cluster 4 demonstrates the most pronounced drop between 2005 and 2014, while Cluster 6 shows a significant decline during the 1995-2004 decade. Cluster 2 displays a continuous decline over the three decades. For instance, in the Béziers region in southern France, within the Astian groundwater body, approximately one-third of the OWs belong to Cluster 4, indicating a decline in groundwater levels during the last period.

The clusters with rising WTD evolution (Clusters 7, 8, and 5) demonstrate increasing groundwater levels at specific points in time. Cluster 7 shows the most substantial rise in groundwater levels during the second decade. OWs in Cluster 8 display a step rise in the first decade, followed by a continuation of rising levels. Cluster 5 indicates a recovery in WTD, with rising levels after a decline during the first decade. For example, in the La Mancha Oriental aquifer within the Jucar River basin, located in an arid climate, the OWs belong to Cluster 5, representing a recovery evolution after initially declining levels.

It is important to note that these examples illustrate the WTD evolutions and do not imply that all OWs within the same cluster follow identical processes. They serve as local examples to elucidate specific WTD dynamics. Among the clusters, the majority (~68%) exhibit stable WTD levels, while 12% experience declining levels at some point, and 20% demonstrate rising levels at some point.

To summarise, the behaviour of groundwater level across the region can be grouped in 9 clusters, being most of them stable groundwater level evolutions. These behaviours are distributed across different climates and latitudes, displaying some hotspots of either declining or rising levels, but mostly a mix of them.

3.3. Drivers analysis

Different groundwater level evolution patterns were identified across the region, which do not necessarily conform to a spatial pattern. A regional perspective was adopted to explore factors and driving components that could account for the variations in trend evolutions, taking into consideration the diverse geographical conditions. To achieve this, comprehensive data encompassing the entire area, primarily sourced from European or Global databases, was compiled. Key variables such as precipitation, evapotranspiration averages, trends, and hydrogeological units were examined. Due to the unavailability of direct groundwater pumping data sources, proxies were utilised, including the distance from wells to irrigated fields and cities, along with the extent of irrigated fields adjacent to the wells. The following section provides a detailed description of the variables that exhibited the highest potential for differentiating the clusters.

3.3.1. Climate, Precipitation and Evapotranspiration

Climate plays a significant role in influencing groundwater dynamics, as observed in our study. The distribution of wells across different climate classifications revealed that the majority (61%) were located in areas classified as temperate climate with no dry season. A smaller portion of wells were situated in temperate climate regions with dry summers (18%) and arid climates (20%), as depicted in Figure 6. When examining the climate distribution by cluster, we found that wells in stable clusters exhibited a greater presence in temperate climates with no

dry season, ranging from 60% to 70%. This distribution was similar to or even higher than the overall distribution across all wells.

Figure 6. Percentage distribution of climate classifications type for all studied observation wells (above) and as the difference (below) between the percentage of each cluster and all the observation wells. Clusters are arranged by stable (left), declining (center) and rising (right).

Conversely, wells in declining clusters were less represented in temperate areas with no dry season (30% to 60%) compared to stable wells. Still, they showed higher representation in arid areas (20% to 40%) compared to the general case. A similar trend was observed for wells with rising levels, as they were less distributed in temperate climates with no dry season (35% to 54%) and more prevalent in arid areas (25% to 50%). These observations highlight the influence of climate on groundwater behaviour within different clusters.

The influence of annual precipitation and evapotranspiration on groundwater dynamics was examined based on our observations. Analysis of the average annual precipitation in proximity to each well, comparing them across groups and clusters, revealed that wells belonging to stable clusters exhibited a higher median annual precipitation (694 mm/y) compared to the declining (623 mm/y) and rising (623 mm/y) clusters (Figure 7). Within the stable clusters, slight differences were observed between clusters, with medians ranging from 687 to 710 mm/y. In contrast, wells in declining clusters displayed a range of medians between 546 and 760 mm/y, while rising clusters ranged from 437 to 640 mm/y. Regarding potential evapotranspiration, the wells in declining clusters had the highest median value of 685 mm/y, followed by rising wells with 660 mm/y, and stable wells with 573 mm/y. Examining the P/PET (precipitation to potential evapotranspiration) ratio, stable clusters exhibited a median value of 1.2, indicating that in the majority of cases, there was more annual water input than evaporative output. Conversely, the declining clusters had a median ratio of 0.85, and the rising clusters had a median ratio of 0.94, suggesting a higher prevalence of wells with more evapotranspiration than precipitation. These precipitation and evapotranspiration distributions further support the observation that stable wells are more prevalent in temperate climates with consistent year-round precipitation, while declining and rising wells are found in areas with lower precipitation and higher potential evapotranspiration.

Figure 7. Interquartile distribution by well and subgroup of average annual precipitation (mm) (top) and evapotranspiration (mm) (middle), as well as P/PET ratio (bottom)

The influence of linear trends in annual precipitation and evapotranspiration on groundwater dynamics was assessed based on our observations. Calculation of the linear regression slope for the studied period provided insights into the overall changes in precipitation and evapotranspiration. Although most trends were not statistically significant, positive slopes indicated an overall increase in precipitation. In terms of precipitation, the general trend for all wells exhibited a positive slope with a median of 0.52 mm/yr. Wells belonging to rising clusters displayed the highest values, with a median slope of 1.29 mm/yr (Figure 8). Within this group, median slopes ranged from 0.85 to 1.43 mm/yr. The stable group had an overall median slope of 0.44 mm/yr, varying within the clusters from 0.33 to 0.62 mm/yr. Conversely, the declining clusters showed a decrease in precipitation with a median slope of -0.13 mm/yr, ranging within the clusters from 0.01 to -1.1 mm/yr. Regarding evapotranspiration, the overall median linear trend for all wells was 1.05 mm/yr. The observed period exhibited smaller differences in the linear trends among groups, with stable clusters having a linear trend of 1.1 mm/yr, while the declining and rising clusters had trends of 0.82 mm/yr and 0.95 mm/yr, respectively. Overall, there was a greater difference in precipitation trends compared to

evapotranspiration trends. Notably, wells belonging to rising clusters displayed higher values of linear precipitation trend, potentially contributing to the observed rise in groundwater levels.

Figure 8. Interquartile distribution by well and subgroup of linear trend slopes for annual precipitation and potential evapotranspiration (mm/yr)

3.3.2. Hydrogeology

The hydrogeological characteristics of the study area play a role in shaping groundwater behaviour, as indicated by our observations. A majority of wells (49%) were situated in highly productive porous aquifers, while 19% were in moderately porous aquifers (Figure 9 9). Highly productive fissured and karst aquifers accounted for 18% of the wells, and moderately productive fissured and karst aquifers comprised 10%. The remaining wells were distributed among highly and moderately fractured aquifers and local aquifers. When examining the hydrogeology distribution by cluster, we found that wells in stable clusters exhibited hydrogeological characteristics similar to the general distribution. In contrast, wells in declining clusters were underrepresented in both highly productive hydrogeologies (porous and fissured-karst), while displaying a higher presence in moderately productive porous and fissured-karst aquifers compared to the overall distribution. On the other hand, wells in the rising levels cluster did not exhibit a clear signature as a distinct group in terms of hydrogeology.

Figure 9. Percentage distribution of hydrogeology type for all studied observation wells and per cluster as the difference between the percentage of each cluster and all the observation wells. Clusters are arranged by stable (left), declining (centre) and rising (right).

3.3.3. Human activities

The influence of anthropogenic factors on groundwater level trends was investigated, considering the available data and proxies for groundwater use. Since direct datasets of groundwater pumping for different purposes were not accessible, proxies were employed to assess potential groundwater use. Proximity to large areas of irrigation (over 1,000 hectares) and the extent of irrigated areas in the vicinity of the wells served as proxies for irrigation, while the distance of wells to cities (settlements larger than 1,500 hectares) was utilised as a proxy for urban influence.

Analysing the distance to irrigation areas, it was observed that wells in stable clusters exhibited the greatest distance, with a median of 13 km, indicating a lower influence from irrigation activities (Figure 10). In contrast, wells in rising and declining clusters were closer to irrigation areas, with median distances of 6 km and 4 km, respectively. Regarding the irrigated area in proximity to the wells, rising clusters displayed the highest values, with a median of 690 hectares, while declining and stable clusters had medians of 260 hectares and 2015 hectares, respectively. Notably, rising clusters with larger irrigated areas were predominantly associated with cereal crops.

Figure 10. Interquartile distribution by well and subgroup of distance to irrigation areas (m) (top) and amount (ha) of irrigated areas in the vicinity of wells

Considering the urban influence, the general median distance from wells to cities was approximately 17 km, which aligned with the distance medians for declining and stable clusters

(18 km and 16 km, respectively) (Figure 11). Rising wells exhibited the greatest distance from cities, with a median of 22 km.

Figure 11. Interquartile distribution by clusters and subgroups of distance to cities (m)

In summary, significant differences were observed among the clusters in terms of anthropogenic influence. Stable clusters were situated farther away from irrigated fields, indicating a lesser impact from water use. Conversely, declining wells exhibited the closest proximity to irrigation areas, suggesting a stronger influence. Rising wells, on the other hand, demonstrated a higher concentration of irrigated areas, particularly for cereal crops, potentially indicating return flow or areas where groundwater extraction is minimal. The influence of cities was most pronounced for rising wells, which were located at a greater distance from urban centres.

4. Closing Remarks

- The results of the study indicate that the majority of piezometers showing no significant trend, but there are significant trends in the depth of water tables across the studied regions, with Spain having the highest percentage of piezometers with a declining trend.
- The study found that piezometers with an declining trend in water table depth exceed those with a rising trend. However, it is important to note that the trend tests reveal the trend along the entire time series, and any comparison should be careful, as the piezometers in the three countries have different starting times of measurement.
- The decade analysis shows a potential process of recovery from some depleting groundwater bodies in the regions, with a decrease in the amount of piezometers with a declining trend and an increase in the amount of piezometers with a rising trend. The spatial distribution of the decade analysis shows a recovery process in the north of France and a more dispersed process in Spain, while Portugal shows a more prevalent concentration of increasing water table depth across the country.
- By grouping wells by their trend results, nine different clusters of groundwater developments were formed, and then subgrouped in stable, declining and rising. They are distributed in the study area.
- When looking into drivers that could explain the regional scale differences, we found that stable wells are relatively more represented in temperate areas with year-long precipitation, while declining and rising wells are more present in arid areas. This is confirmed by the average precipitation and potential evapotranspiration data, signalling a ratio (P/PET) above one for the stable clusters and below one for declining and rising wells.
- When looking at linear trends of precipitation, rising wells showed the highest slope of change in comparison with the other groups. While no significant trend was found, an increase of precipitation between 1985-2014 could explain some of the rising level behaviour.

- In terms of hydrogeology, the biggest observed difference was that stable clusters are located more in highly productive aquifers (mainly porous and fissured-kast) while declining ones are comparatively more present in moderately productive aquifers.
- In terms of human impacts on groundwater trends: stable clusters located farther from irrigated fields, indicating reduced water use impact. Declining wells in close proximity to irrigation areas, suggesting stronger anthropogenic influence. Rising wells exhibit higher concentration of irrigated areas, potentially indicating minimal groundwater extraction or return flow.

5. References

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